

Electrochemical Performance of Al-Mn₂O₃ Based Electrode Materials

Noor Ul Ain Bhatti, M. Junaid Khan, Javed Ahmad, Murtaza Saleem, Shahid M. Ramay, Saadat A. Siddiqi

Abstract—Manganese oxide is being recently used as electrode material for rechargeable batteries. In this study, Al incorporated Mn₂O₃ compositions were synthesized to study the effect of Al doping on electrochemical performance of host material. Structural studies were carried out using X-ray diffraction analysis to confirm the phase stability and explore the lattice parameters, crystallite size, lattice strain, density and cell volume. Morphology and composition were analyzed using field emission scanning electron microscope and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, respectively. Dynamic light scattering analysis was performed to observe the average particle size of the compositions. FTIR measurements exhibit the O-Al-O and O-Mn-O and Al-O bonding and with increasing the concentration of Al, the vibrational peaks of Mn-O become sharper. An enhanced electrochemical performance was observed in compositions with higher Al content.

Keywords—Mn₂O₃, electrode materials, energy storage and conversion, electrochemical performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE tailoring of layered oxide materials have been widely discussed subject as a source for portable energy storage devices. Numerous materials have been proposed that proved to be a good candidate for advanced technologies including batteries, fuel cells, solar cells and super capacitors [1], [2]. The advancement in search of energy storage materials enforce us to make cost efficient and maximum storage capacity materials which could be used for portable electronic devices and hybrid electronic vehicles. In recent electronic applications, lithium ion batteries are preferably used as they have high coulombic energy efficiency, magnificent low self-discharge rate and lack of memory effect [3], [4]. Graphite is enormously used as commercial material for lithium ion batteries but due to its low storage capacity, energy, power density, longer life cycle and improved safety there is a need to search new materials as layered oxides as a use for better electrode material [5]. To enhance storage capacity of Li ion batteries, transition metal oxides in nano-structured materials

have been extensively studied [6], [7]. Among all transition metal oxides [8] such as manganese oxide [9], [10], ruthenium oxide [11], cobalt oxide [12], [13], nickel oxide [14], copper oxide [15], manganese oxide is considered as the most reliable electrode material because of their abundance, non-toxicity, low cost, multiple high theoretical capacitance and environmental compatibility. Ruthenium oxide is toxic and other materials have also limited in their use so we prefer manganese oxide [16], [17]. A number of research studies have been done on synthesis of nanostructured manganese oxide with different experimental techniques such as physical vapor deposition, chemical bath deposition, sputtering [18] and sol-gel methods [19]. Elemental doping of simple metal oxides to form mixed metal oxides has been a way to boost up their electrochemical activities, electronic conductivity and to minimize their cost efficiency. In this case, binary systems doping is preferable such as NiMn, MnCo [20], MnFe [21], NiCo [22], SnAl oxides and ternary metal oxides systems like Mn-Ni-Co [23], [24], Co-Ni-Cu [25] and Mn-Ni-Cu oxides [26]. In present research work, we study sol-gel synthesized nanostructured Mn₂O₃ with doping combination of Al. The samples are physically characterized by X-Ray diffraction (XRD), field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), dynamic light scattering, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and electrochemical measurements. The effect of Al substitution on all these properties of Mn₂O₃ was precisely studied and found that electrochemical performance was significantly enhanced.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

A. Synthesis

Al doped Mn₂O₃ nanostructured compositions were synthesized using well established sol-gel based fuel agent assisted self-combustion technique. Stoichiometric molar ratios of analytical research grade aluminium nitrate [Al(NO₃)₂·9H₂O] and manganese nitrate [Mn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O] were use as the sources of Al and Mn, respectively. In this preparation, glycine was used as the fuel agent. Calculated molar amounts of reagents for undoped and Al doped Mn₂O₃ were weighed on a precise digital balance and subsequently dissolved in 25 ml distilled water. The solution was kept on hot place at 250 °C with constant stirring inside a clean fume hood environment. The temperature of the attained gel was raised to 350 °C and stirring was subsequently stopped. Fine powder of brownish black color was obtained after intense exothermic combustion reaction. The resulting products were dried and calcinated at 600 °C for 4 hours, subsequently, a

Noor Ul Ain Bhatti, M. Junaid Khan, and Javed Ahmad are with the Laboratory of Experimental and Theoretical Physics, Department of Physics, Bahauddin Zakariya University (60800), Multan, Pakistan.

Murtaza Saleem is with the Department of Physics, Syed Babar Ali School of Sciences and Engineering (SBASSE), Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS), Opposite Sector U, DHA, Lahore 54792, Pakistan.

Shahid M. Ramay is with the College of Science, Department of Physics and Astronomy, King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Saadat A. Siddiqi is with the Interdisciplinary Research Centre in Biomedical Materials, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, M.A. Jinnah Campus, Lahore-54600, Pakistan (Corresponding Author; phone: +92-300-4866616; e-mail: saadat.anwar@ciitlahore.edu.pk).

dark brownish powder was obtained for each composition. The powder was grinded well using mortar and pestle until fine, homogenous and uniform sized particles were achieved.

B. Characterizations

Structural studies were carried out using XRD instrument (Bruker D-2 Phaser) operating at 30 kV and 10 mA using Cu K-alpha radiation ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and a step scan size of 0.05° . A FESEM (FEI Nova 450) was used to observe the morphology of the samples. Qualitative and quantitative elemental compositions were confirmed using EDS spectrometry (Oxford Instrument Inca X-Act). FTIR analysis were carried out using Bruker Alpha instrument. Chinstruments 660E was used to extract the first charge-discharge curves and cyclic performance of all the synthesized compositions.

Fig. 1 XRD spectra of undoped and Al doped compositions

The XRD spectra of undoped and Al doped Mn_2O_3 are shown in Fig. 1. All the peaks in XRD patterns are exactly matched with the host Mn_2O_3 standard pattern containing JCPD card number 76-0150. However, some traces of oxides of Al were observed and clearly appeared in composition with highest content of Al and this showing some different behavior as compared to other spectra. It is clear that there are

visible peak shifts to higher angle in the spectrum which is consistent to the previously reported substitutions [27], [28] with lower ionic radii. Crystallite size, cell volume, lattice constant and lattice strain were calculated and observed a significant variation in it with doping of Al content. Crystallite size and cell volume was observed as 43-53 nm and $784\text{-}824 \text{ \AA}^3$, respectively as shown in Table I. A significant variation in lattice constant ($9.22\text{-}9.38 \text{ \AA}$) and lattice strain ($2.64\text{-}15.57$) was also observed revealed the doping of Al content in to Mn_2O_3 structure.

The microstructural studies were carried out using FESEM equipped with EDX detector. Fig. 2 presents the FESEM micrographs of undoped and Al doped Mn_2O_3 samples. It is visible through images that morphologies are oriented in non-uniform arrangement but they have distinct boundaries and clear shapes like microspheres and fillets with some compact shapes, as well as few cavities in them. Particles are present in random sizes which are estimated as 94.57 nm for $\text{Al}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{1.9}\text{O}_3$, 144 nm for $\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Mn}_{1.7}\text{O}_3$ and 172 nm for $\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_3$ samples. The particles in Al doped Mn_2O_3 are observed to be arranged more densely because of relatively smaller size of Al.

Fig. 3 represents the EDX spectra for all of the four samples. The EDX analysis reveals that Mn, O and Al contents are present in the approximate stoichiometric ratios in the samples, which ensure the incorporation of Al constituents in the host Mn_2O_3 structure. Traces of very small carbon content might visible just because of the sample remnant. Quantitative EDX analysis is approximately according to the dissolved molar ratio for added elements in all samples as given in Table II.

FTIR spectra of Mn_2O_3 and doped with different concentrations of Al are studied in the range $400\text{-}550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as shown in Fig. 4 (a) which reveals the presence of O-Mn-O and O-Al-O stretching modes. The transmittance spectra of undoped and doped samples have considerable differences among them. Most of the transmission bands are stretched between the wavelength $400\text{-}550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The wide band appearing from 500 cm^{-1} onward correspond to vibrational frequencies of coordinate O-Al-O bond [29]. Low frequency band in the vicinity of 419 cm^{-1} correspond to the change in O-Mn-O bond angle [30]. Other bands in the range $400\text{-}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is correspond to the Al-O vibrations [31]. As we increase Al concentration, we observe that Mn-O vibrational peak at $\sim 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ appear to be sharper.

TABLE I
LATTICE CONSTANT, CRYSTALLITE SIZE, CELL VOLUME, LATTICE STRAIN AND DENSITY OF COMPOSITIONS

Sample	Lattice Constants (\AA)	Crystallite Size (nm)	Cell Volume (\AA^3)	Lattice strain ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Density (gm^{-3})
Undoped	9.38	44	824.50	2.64	5.08
$\text{Al}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{1.9}\text{O}_3$	9.27	53	795.82	12.04	6.17
$\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Mn}_{1.7}\text{O}_3$	9.22	53	784.7	15.57	6.26
$\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_3$	9.27	45	796.3	11.75	6.17

Fig. 2 FESEM micrographs of undoped and Al doped compositions

Fig. 3 EDX spectra of undoped and Al doped compositions

TABLE II
EDX ELEMENTAL COMPOSITIONAL MEASUREMENTS

	Undoped		$\text{Al}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{1.9}\text{O}_3$		$\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Mn}_{1.7}\text{O}_3$		$\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_3$	
	At. %	Wt. %	At. %	Wt. %	At. %	Wt. %	At. %	Wt. %
O	62.27	34.08	64.15	37.53	63.56	37	64.28	40.69
Al	0	0	1.69	1.66	4.32	4.24	8.78	9.38
Mn	34.34	64.53	29.17	58.61	28.64	57.24	21.86	47.52
C	3.39	1.39	4.99	2.2	3.48	1.51	5.08	2.41
Total				100				

It is well understood that shape and structure of materials have direct influence on the electrochemical properties in respect of cyclability and performance [32]. However, there

are yet few works reported to enhance the electrochemical performance with additional doping in Mn_2O_3 like materials. The electrochemical performance of all $\text{Al}_x\text{Mn}_{2-x}\text{O}_3$ compositions was obtained to determine the Al doping effect. Figs. 4 (b), (c) show the first cycle curves for charging and discharging process of all the samples. A wide sharp plateau can be seen in all first discharge curves at various values. The similar fact was also observed in some previous reports [33]. The obtained initial discharge capacity for Al substituted compositions is higher than that of un-doped Mn_2O_3 . The lowest charge capacity was observed for Mn_2O_3 while highest for composition doped with maximum value of Al. Cycling

performance of all compositions was measured as shown in Fig. 4 (d). Saturation in capacity was reached after a sharp initial decrease. It was found that Al doped compositions show

enhanced capacity values after maximum number of cycles. It can be realized that Al substitution in Mn_2O_3 improves the electrochemical properties.

Fig. 4 (a) FTIR spectra and (b-d) electrochemical performance of undoped and Al doped compositions

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Al incorporated Mn_2O_3 compositions were successfully synthesized to study the effect of Al doping on electrochemical performance of host material. XRD analysis confirm the phase stability and explore the variation in lattice parameters, crystallite size, lattice strain, density and cell volume. Morphology and elemental composition analysis were in good agreement with the dissolved concentrations of Al in host material. The FTIR results exhibit the O-Al-O and O-Mn-O and Al-O bonding and with increasing the concentration of Al, the vibrational peaks become sharper. An indication of enhanced electrochemical performance in compositions with incorporation of Al content is considerably important for application point of view.

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